

THE VALUE OF THE EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER IN A MULTIDISCIPLINARY PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATION

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Annotation: This article talks about the importance of the educational cluster in a multidisciplinary preschool organization.

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As you know, in each specialized multidisciplinary preschool organization, work is underway to correct speech disorders, corrective work with mentally retarded children, children with cerebral palsy, children with visual impairments and hearing impairments.

Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", PF-5198 dated September 30, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the management of preschool education" Presidential Decree No. PP-3261 dated 9 September 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of preschool education", October 13, 2020 "On measures to further improve the education system for children with special educational needs";

Decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 19, 2017 No. 528 "On measures to improve the activities of preschool educational institutions", May 13, 2019 No. 391 "On measures to further improve the activities of preschool educational institutions" and other related activities defined in the regulatory documents .

In practice, work with children with developmental disorders occurs in special multidisciplinary institutions. In specialized institutions, working specialists develop children of each psychological and pedagogical side.

Children develop while playing, which is why defectologists give meaning to the work of speech therapy classes for the correction of children.

Kindergarten and school are connected to each other. Their job is to bring up children and give knowledge. A cluster is a related work of a kindergarten and a school. Each institution operates according to its own rules. But, the goal of every institution is to develop the child.

A well-developed child gives good academic results. And how a person tries to show his best side.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2018 No. PP-3955 "On measures to improve the management of preschool education", as well as to further improve preschool education, a number of decisions were made. the Cabinet of Ministers in order to create favorable conditions for the education, upbringing and integration of children, as well as children in need of rehabilitation and rehabilitation.

- This Regulation defines the goals and objectives, rights, duties and responsibilities of multidisciplinary specialized preschool educational organizations (hereinafter referred to as specialized preschool organizations) and preschool educational organizations of a combined type (hereinafter referred to as a combined preschool organization), as well as the procedure for organizing their activities.

- Specialized preschool organizations and preschool organizations of a combined type carry out their activities in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On preschool education and upbringing" and other laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, resolutions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan , resolutions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, State requirements for the development of children of early and preschool age, this Regulation and its charter.

- The activities of specialized preschool organizations are aimed at obtaining preschool education for children with physical or mental developmental disabilities, as well as their upbringing and rehabilitation.

The activity of preschool organizations of a combined type is aimed at organizing joint education and upbringing in one organization in separate groups of children with physical or mental developmental disorders and children without developmental disorders.

In a preschool organization of a combined type, inclusive groups can be organized.

- Specialized preschool organizations and preschool organizations of a combined type can be state and non-state.

- Accreditation of a specialized preschool organization and a preschool organization of a combined type is carried out by an authorized state body on the basis of attestation in the manner prescribed by law.

- The state specialized preschool organization and the combined type preschool organization are legal entities, have a seal with the image of the State Emblem of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its name in the state language and a stamp, an independent balance sheet, budgetary and non-budgetary treasury personal accounts.
- A non-state specialized preschool organization and a combined type preschool organization are legal entities, have separate property, have an independent balance sheet, are liable for their obligations with the property at their disposal, and may have a seal and a stamp with their name.
- A non-state specialized preschool organization and a preschool organization of a combined type carry out educational activities from the moment of obtaining a license in the manner prescribed by law.

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